

Overall study design

Title of the study	Erster Test		
Document creation date	03/21/2023	Corresponding Email	gerhard.liebisch@ukr.de
Principle investigator	GL	Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Targeted
Institution	UKR	Clinical	Yes

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	2-phase system	Bligh&Dyer
pH adjustment	None	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes

Analytical platform

MS type	QQQ	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	1
MS vendor	Waters	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	Low resolution
Ion source	ESI	Resolution in Da at MS2	1
Direct type	Syringe	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No
MS Level	MS2		

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	Yes
Type of Blanks	Extraction blank, Injection blank	Type of QC sample	Sample pool, Reference material

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Precision	Yes
Lipid recovery	Yes	Accuracy	Yes
Dynamic quantification range	Yes	Guidelines followed	None
Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	Yes		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Available on request	Additional comments	-
Raw data upload	Available on request		

Sample Descriptions

Plasma sample pools / Human / Plasma

Provided information	-	Additives	None
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	No

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) PS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PS	Background check at MS2	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check isomer overlap	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Polarity mode	Positive	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Fragments for identification		Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Fragment name	NL 185		
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
MS2 verified by standard	No		

1) PS[M+H]⁺ / For additional separation methods/analytical dimension

Quantitative	Yes	Response correction	No
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Type I isotope correction	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) for MS2		Limit of quantification	S/N ratio
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous class	
PS 28:0	NL 185	all PS species	
Type of quantification	Calibration line	Normalization to reference	No
Type of calibration line	Matrix based	Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Species calibration line	PC 34:1, PS 36:2,	Batch correction	No